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**INCREASING THE IMPORTANCE AND ROLE OF
FOREIGN LANGUAGES IN THE PERIOD OF
GLOBALIZATION AND SUSTAINABLE
DEVELOPMENT OF THE NEW UZBEKISTAN**
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Last but not the least, the aforementioned challenges require more than one parties to be involved in the process of handling since teachers solely are less likely to overcome these obstacles all by themselves. The intervention of educational authorities, fellow educators and students would make the process much smoother and more feasible to happen.

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THE ISSUES OF DEVELOPING EFFECTIVE METHODS OF PROFESSIONALLY ORIENTED EDUCATION ARE BECOMING INCREASINGLY RELEVANT IN THE FORMATION AND OBJECTIVE ASSESSMENT OF UNIVERSAL COMPETENCIES FOR FUTURE SPECIALISTS IN THE FIELD OF ECONOMICS.

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Abstract

In leading higher educational institutions worldwide, the primary focus is on the use of differentiated education to ensure the integration of science, education, and industry in the process of professional training for future specialists. In this regard, the development of effective teaching methods for professionally oriented education in universities is becoming increasingly relevant.

Keywords: professionally oriented education, differentiated education for specialists in economics, continuous education improvement, international standards

Introduction

The expansion of international cooperation in various spheres leads to higher demands for the preparation of university graduates, including their proficiency in foreign languages as a tool for information activity. Therefore, the collective use of non-standard forms, methods, and learning tools in the educational environment plays an important role in the formation and objective assessment of universal competencies for future specialists in the field of economics. In recent years, future specialists in our republic have the opportunity to communicate in foreign languages, stay up to date with new scientific discoveries and technological trends, master modern technologies, and thereby enhance their professional skills. Mass media, the increasing flow of foreign-language Internet information through the global computer network, presents future specialists with the necessity to master large amounts of information in a foreign language in order to use it for solving professional tasks.

In this context, the development of effective methods for professionally oriented education in universities is becoming increasingly relevant. "Further improvement of continuous education, continuation of the policy of training highly qualified personnel according to modern labor market needs" and "improving the quality and efficiency of higher education institutions by implementing international standards for assessing the quality of education and personnel preparation." This is a substantive characteristic of the training of future economists, expanding the possibilities of using technologies in education within higher education, providing students with deep knowledge in their chosen specialty,

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and forming and developing professional competencies in teaching through differentiated educational programs.

Research Methods

The issues of professional training for future higher education specialists and the development of abilities have been of interest to researchers in our country. Scientists such as Zh.Zh. Jalolov, G.Kh. Bakiyeva, U.Kh. Khoshimov, T.K. Satorov, S. Saidaliev, G.T. Makhkamova, L.T. Akhmedova, K.Zh. Riskulova, I.M. Tukhatsinov, and U.U. Jumanzarov conducted their research in this field.

Analysis and results

Systematic study of pedagogical and scientific literature in terms of the research problem, critical analysis of higher education DTC (Differentiated Training Content), qualification requirements, curricula, and programs, comparative analysis of scientific-methodical sources in information technology science, monitoring of the educational process, conducting surveys, experimental verification methods, and mathematical-statistical processing of the obtained results have been used. To achieve the goals set in the field of professionally oriented education, using a foreign language as an example, it is necessary to define the main forms of teaching and learning and the linguistic-didactic conditions for their implementation using professionally oriented differentiated education in a foreign language when training students in educational institutions. The scientific substantiation of information-methodological conditions for teaching English based on a differentiated approach in the higher education system; Improving the methodology for teaching foreign languages based on a differentiated approach; Improving the systemic-contextual model for using professionally oriented differentiated education in teaching foreign languages; Developing methods for improving students' foreign language learning skills based on the main methodological principles of the differentiated approach. In the context of using professionally oriented differentiated education when preparing students in economics, the model for implementing the process of independent learning in a foreign language is considered, based on the differentiation (diagnostic and intellectual) of the integrative content of education, purposeful and active acquisition of new information. For each multi-level subgroup, a systemic, professionally oriented differentiated methodological complex is defined, with the development of individual training sessions, exercises aimed at developing professional skills, communication, and independent work tasks, and their integration into the process of preparing future specialists, as well as the possibility of using them in training and retraining courses.

Conclusion

Adapting professional-methodological training of specialists worldwide to modern requirements, using differentiated education in foreign languages, developing students' professional competencies in higher education institutions, ensuring scientific-pedagogical and methodological training, meeting the industry's need for competitive specialists, and ensuring higher education are essential demands of the time. Improving professional training for future specialists based on modern approaches is an important factor in elevating the quality of higher education to a new level. To achieve this, it is necessary to ensure that higher education meets international standards and to develop and implement innovative pedagogical technologies in the professional training of qualified specialists according to social needs.

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THE "COMMUNICATIVE CIRCLE" METHOD IN TEACHING ENGLISH IN TECHNICAL UNIVERSITIES.

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Abstract

The article analyzes the problems that arise when teaching English at a technical university and describes a new integrated method of teaching listening, reading and speaking, called the "Communicative Circle" method. During the training, students gradually receive more complex tasks to practice speaking and texts for reading and listening, and the entire learning process is based on expanding the professional and scientific knowledge of students in the field of technical university.

The article concludes that the developed methodology is more effective, which indicates a higher level of English proficiency, confidence and expansion of professional horizons of students studying using the "Communicative Circle" methodology.

Key words: activity-based approach, "Communicative Circle" method, integration of speech activity, development of listening, reading and speaking skills, three levels of awareness.

Currently, the problem of developing communication skills is given much attention in a variety of scientific fields, ranging from training students whose communication skills will be in demand in the labor market to communication skills, presentations for foreign language proficiency. The main article focuses on the last of these problems. Unfortunately, at present, technical specialists in Uzbekistan often face the need to teach students who have only Basic English skills. As our teaching practice shows, the main problem is related to basic speech skills involved both in students' consideration of texts in English and in their comprehension. Without repeating writing in the learning process, the main emphasis is placed on three main types of verbal skills: listening, reading and speaking, because, firstly, their use involves more consistent responses from the listener/reader/speaker (writing is usually stretched out in time). In addition, as a rule, causes greater difficulties in learning, and, secondly, they are most often